

Electrified Ice Needles Fast Formation under the Influence of Electric Fields

Leandra P. Santos¹, André Galembeck² and Fernando Galembeck^{1,3}

1- Galembetech Ltda., 2- Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, 3- Universidade Estadual de Campinas
leandrapereiradossantos@gmail.com, andre@ufpe.br, fernagal@unicamp.br

Keywords: atmospheric electrification, phase separation, ice needles and dendrites.

1. ABSTRACT

Atmospheric electricity formation and storage occur in humid air under pressure and temperature gradients, producing the electric fields that trigger lightning. Many authors discussed the relevant events and mechanisms delivering atmospheric electrification, but a comprehensive picture has not yet emerged. This work describes experimental and theoretical results on the effect of electric fields on water vapor, evidencing the positive feedback between electricity and water vapor condensation progress. Vapor condensation under a field produces electrified needles and dendrites under conditions relevant to the formation of atmospheric electricity.

Two new findings explain the enhancement of vapor condensation under a field due to the decrease or elimination of the energy barrier of the nucleation of the condensed phase. Water vapor clusters acquire charge under the electric field, thus decreasing the surface tension of water and ice nuclei and thus enhancing nuclei formation and growth rates, following the Classical Nucleation Theory (CNT). Beyond, new experimental evidence shows the participation of a non-classical (NC) phase-separation mechanism triggered by the electric field. The two agents produce needle-shaped ice that is not the prevalent crystal habit.

Increasing the rates of phase change also increases the rate of electrification in any environment; following discoveries initiated by Volta and Lord Armstrong long ago and later verified by other authors that observed spontaneously electrified ice jumping in different contexts, the excess charge of partially condensed steam exiting vapor turbines or of water evaporating or condensing at metallic surfaces, growing as an active research area.

The Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars effect predicts that any isolated droplet of water, ice crystal, or aerosol particle within the atmosphere should always carry a charge since it is under a non-zero electric potential gradient. An additional factor is the lower binding energy of H^+ ions at water or ice surfaces than OH^- .

Beyond water, non-polar substances like carnauba wax and naphthalene also undergo electrification during freezing. On the practical side, some industries currently explore the electro-freezing effect.

The present work adds new experimental and theoretical results to an already large but dispersed body of information showing how electrification and phase change feedback mutually, to the point of provoking Coulomb explosions.

2. INTRODUCTION

Ice needles are the crystal habit found in young sea ice formation [1] as frost flowers [2]. Frost [3] and periglacial

ground ice [4] show narrow ice slivers up to several centimeters long. The observation of elongated ice crystals in stratiform clouds during field projects in the North Atlantic and over the Great Lakes occurring within large cells extending for kilometers, in the $0^\circ > T > -6^\circ \text{C}$ temperature range [5] raised the following questions: *"What is the mechanism of ice nucleation in the cells of dendrites and needles? Why does the fraction of the dendrites or needles reach 100% in a particular place while a few kilometers away the concentration of dendrites or needles is zero? Are needles and dendrites growing from existing irregularly shaped ice particles, falling from above, or does the nucleation of the needles and dendrites occur inside these cells?"* Needle prevalence in a narrow temperature range was discussed in a recent report of the BAIRS II project [6], involving measurements in many winter storms. An aircraft field program in Texas [7] detected elongated ice shapes in material collected from cumulus clouds at -6°C . Studies on the growth of snow crystals within laboratory cloud chambers revealed a complex dependence of crystal habit on temperature. One study showed ice shape-changing sharply six times over the temperature range of 0 to -25°C [8]. These observations refer to the early stages of crystal growth and reveal a difference in the relative surface diffusion rates across the basal and prism faces. A comprehensive habit diagram [9] covering the 0 to -70°C temperature range and low ice supersaturation shows the formation of many different habits closer to 0°C : from plates (0 to -4°C) to columns (-4 to -8°C) to plates (-8 to -22°C), in agreement with previously published habit diagrams.

Another relevant topic in atmospheric ice crystal formation is secondary ice production (SIP) [10] explaining the mismatch between ice crystal concentrations in natural clouds at modest supercooling and the particle number of primary ice nucleating particles. The former are orders of magnitude larger than the latter, stimulating laboratory, modeling, theoretical, and field investigations [11-13]. Different mechanisms were proposed to explain the significant difference between nuclei and grown-up particle concentrations, including drop shattering, rime splintering, collisional break-up, and sublimation fragmentation. So, the currently prevalent mechanisms are based on the rupture and subdivision of pre-existing ice or water. Other field observations in the temperature range from 0 to -15°C showed high concentrations of small pristine ice particles at -0.5°C , which formed just above the melting layer [14] The authors concluded that *"the airborne in-situ observations could clearly support only the freezing-drop-shattering mechanism"* and presented a conceptual model for this mechanism.

Interestingly, the intensive research on secondary ice production mechanisms has not explicitly included the associated effects of particle electrification or molecular dipole orientation [15] nor its feedback on ice nucleation and growth. Bartlett et al. in 1965 [16] already noted the omission of charge separation phenomena in atmospheric ice

formation in part of the literature. However, Saunders [17] reviewed many works presenting various charge separation mechanisms, including their respective contributions to the macroscopic electric structure of clouds.

The discovery of the electrification of water and vapor during phase changes dates from two centuries ago [18]. That explains observations made in different contexts, e.g., in vapor turbines [19] and the impressive ejection of negatively charged ice fragments from surfaces growing by intense water vapor deposition [20,21] in partial support of earlier observations by Findeisen and Findeisen [22,23]. An external potential applied to growing dendrites (at -15°C , the peak of the ice dendrite growth regime) increases tip velocity, but potential growth instability sets in above a threshold [24,25]. Other findings by Libbrecht et al. are the stabilization of dendrite growth rates by structural deformation driven by surface tension [26] and the measurement of surface attachment kinetics for faceted crystal growth [27]. Recent work on ice growth from vapor at -5°C [28] verified the electric potential's significant effect on growing crystals.

In a broader context, charge separation is a universal feature of any system containing an interface, like the atmospheric ice particles, water droplets, and rime. It takes place by different mechanisms in different phenomena, including the Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars effect [29] that predicts charge trapping at any interface. Charge separation in liquid-solid interfaces is paramount in colloid chemistry [30] and nanotechnology, while contact electrification in dielectrics is currently a matter of intense debate. The present authors recently published a comprehensive review of this topic [31].

Electrofreezing [32-35] depends on the interplay between phase growth [36] and charge separation in the water-ice interface since interfacial electric fields can raise freezing temperatures by more than 15°C using blocked electrodes to prevent current flow [37]. That is currently a topic of interest in the food industry [38,39]. Moreover, electrocrystallization of solid phases during electrochemical reactions has received attention from electrochemists [40].

The reciprocal effect is charge separation due to freezing [41] or melting, which discovery precedes electrofreezing [42]. Non-aqueous systems, such as carnauba wax and naphthalene [43] also show charge separations across melting interfaces, and they are part of the broader topic of charge separation during phase transitions [44].

This paper shows the positive feedback between atmospheric electrification and the condensation of water vapor: electric fields induce the rapid formation of electrified ice needles and dendrites that further contribute to increasing atmospheric electricity. Moreover, it presents explanations for all the involved events.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

Fig. 1 presents three experimental set-ups that allow the observation and documentation of the events when cold nitrogen gas emerging from the boiling liquid meets the laboratory atmosphere.

Room temperature, humidity, and pressure were $(20 \pm 2)^{\circ}\text{C}$, $(60 \pm 5)\%$, and $(702 \pm 5)\text{ mmHg}$, respectively. A K-type thermocouple fixed to a movable arm measured the

temperature at different points within the experimental areas shown in Fig. 1, including the volume where the condensation layer occurs and the surfaces where ice is formed. Temperatures range from 3 to 11°C in the condensation layer and between -12 and -3°C in the plane, determined by the Dewar rim and other ice-covered areas. These measurements show that water aerosol formation occurs just above 0°C , while the needle and dendrite formation temperature under the field is just below zero. Thus, ice formation occurs under low supersaturation.

Fig. 1. Schematic drawings (left) and pictures (right) of the three experimental set-ups used in this work. Black arrows indicate the electric field direction, while blue arrows indicate electrical contacts.

Fig. 1a shows a stainless-steel Dewar bottle filled with liquid nitrogen below an aluminum plate measuring $30 \times 20 \times 0.1$ cm horizontally held on two blocks of polyethylene foam, 5.5 cm above the Dewar. A conductor wire connected that to the ground. The aluminum plate receives high voltage from a Hypot DC Instrum (São Paulo, SP) or a CZE 1000R Spellman (Hauppauge, NY) high-voltage power supply creating an electric field of 1 to 5.5 kV/cm. Fig. 1b shows a stainless-steel beaker filled with liquid nitrogen on a polypropylene box placed within a rigid cardboard box measuring $24.5 \times 16 \times 13.5$ cm. The two opposite side internal walls of the box were lined with a graphite-coated Kraft paper sheet. The sheet on the right side was connected to a high voltage power supply. In contrast, the sheet on the left was grounded creating an approximately horizontal

electric field ranging from 0.3 to 1.8 kV/cm (outside the volume disturbed by the metal cup). Fig. 1c shows a glass test tube connected to the high-voltage power supply by an alligator clip and placed in the top center of a grounded Dewar filled with liquid nitrogen. Test tube walls are thus positively biased since the glass surfaces are electrically conductive above 45% relative humidity [45]. This creates an electric field radially distributed around the test tube, whose intensity varies from 1 to 6 kV/cm.

Video recording with a Cannon camera and a microscope documents the events at different scales. Video editing with software allows the extraction of the frames or sequences showing interesting events like particle appearance, growth, and motion within the electric field. Quantitative information on particle dimensions and positions yields data on particle growth rates, velocities, and weights. Fitting this data on standard electrostatic equations delivers particle charge, charge density, and electrostatic potential at particle surfaces.

4. RESULTS

The contact between moist room air and the cold nitrogen vapor emerging from the containers always produces aerosol clouds within a temperature gradient. A thin snow layer then coats the cold surfaces, analogous to those commonly observed on surfaces cooled below 0 °C in contact with the warmer ambient atmosphere.

4.1 Field enhancement of ice formation

Applying an electric field produces a rapid increase in the thickness of the deposited ice layer following the appearance of ice needles and dendrites sitting on the surfaces. Some examples appear in Fig. 2, showing the needle alignment with the electric field. That suggests using needle position, direction, and shape to indicate of environmental electric field lines, including curved needles.

Fig. 2. Ice needle formation under various conditions.

Fig. 2a-c shows pictures of a metal beaker filled with liquid nitrogen at various times. Fig. 2d displays the rim of a Dewar vase under a horizontal metal plate with a supercooled droplet cloud floating above the vase. Applying 10 kV to the plate above the Dewar produces the ice needles appearing in Fig. 2e. Needles formed at the outer wall of the glass tube are in Fig. 2f, and their magnified images are in Fig. 2g-h.

Examining successive video frames in Fig. 3 a-c shows that the growing dendrites slowly collapse under their weight. Fig. 3 d-f shows that the upper dendrite branches grow faster than the lower ones.

Fig. 3. Dendrites and needle growth patterns: a-f: six frames from the same area, extracted from a thirteen-second sequence. A growing dendrite at the left side collapses, falling in the center of the image. The top branches of taller dendrites (within yellow ellipses) grow faster than the ice elements in the lower dendrite regions (highlighted by red ellipses).

The needles and dendrites respond to field switching on and off in many ways. After switching off, the blunt needles and elongated dendrites observed under the field relax under their weight. Then, many dendrites change to sintered blocks of porous ice, while other dendrites and needles recover their shapes, when the field is on, as seen in the set of successive video frames in Fig. 4.

In Fig. 4a, the field is on, and the dendrites stretch upwards, but in Figs. 4b-d, bend downwards progressively (collapsed dendrites indicated by red arrows). Some dendrite fragments jump toward the upper plate when the field is on in Fig. 4e. Some remaining dendrites remain collapsed, but others stretch again (see elongated structures within yellow circles, Fig 4e-f). The broader features of the profile of the ice bed surface persist in Fig. 4a to f, but the detailed dendrite arms and needles are not. That is not surprising since dendrite sintering should occur when the collapsed dendrites touch each other. Following the observations made from Figs. 3 and 4, it follows that faster ice-layer growths results from enhanced ice and dendrite formation followed by dendrite collapse and sintering.

Fig. 4. Successive video frames of the same area show the electric field's effect on dendrites formed on the Dewar rim. The yellow circles indicate the mobile dendrites.

Other examples of particle ejection and trajectory within the field are in Fig. 5. Four consecutive movie frames, arranged clockwise, are in Fig. 5 a-d, where the time difference between the frames is 0.05 seconds. Fig. 5 f, h are magnified cuts from Fig. 5 e, g. Vertical yellow arrows show the needle from whose tip the ice particle departed. In contrast, the gray arrows indicate the ice particle raster or its landing at the biased electrode surface g-h. The potential difference between the left and right sides of the box is 20 kV, and the box width is 16 cm. Fig. 5 i-k shows ice particles ejected from the wall of the biased test tube, and Fig. 5 l-n are the respective magnifications.

Some frames show the streak produced by the fast particle motion revealing its trajectory and allowing the calculation of particle speed. Particle motion within a field indicates that the particle carries an electric charge, is a dipole or both. Some publications refer to the formation of macroscopic dipoles in liquid water and ice due to molecular water dipoles' alignment under the applied field. However, that still needs direct supporting evidence.

4.1 Electric properties from video images

This group has previously shown that water acquires a net electric charge under an electric field, even when suspended in the air and out of contact with any electrified surface. Indeed, this follows from the thermodynamic condition of equilibrium expressed by the electrochemical potential, stating that water under a positive potential contains excess OH^- ions. Still, a negative potential produces excess H^+ ions, following (1), where μ_i is the electrochemical potential of ion i in its environment, μ_i^0 is its value in standard conditions, a_i is its activity, z_i is the charge, F is the Faraday constant, and φ is the local electric potential:

$$\mu_i = \mu_i^0 + RT \ln a_i + z_i F \varphi \quad (1)$$

Fig. 5. Video frame sequences show ice needles leaving the ice beds toward the electrodes.

In a needle or dendrite, excess ions at the dendrite migrate driven by the field, producing a dipole, but they distribute uniformly in the absence of the field.

Ice needle images extracted from the video frames allow the measurement of the cylindrical needle length and diameter, followed by the calculation of the needle surface area, volume and weight. Some sequences show ice flying along the field [36] that allows the calculation of needle speeds during their electrophoretic motion. Knowledge of the field strength, needle weight and speed yields the electric charge and charge surface density on the needle.

Other frame sequences show ice plucked from the apparatus surface, along the vertical field [46]. In this case, the needle weight is lower than the electric force that pulled it. This allows the calculation of the lower limit for the needle charge and needle charge density. Knowing charge density for the needles and using Poisson equation yields the electric field at the needle surface. The detailed application of the two methods is described in recent publications from this group [36,46] converging to the same conclusion: ice particles formed within an electric field are strongly electrified. Calculated surface charge densities range from 0.64 to $1.25 \times 10^{-6} \text{ C.m}^{-2}$, corresponding to electric fields within the 75 to 147 kV.m^{-1} range. Thus, ice particles formed under a field store charge reaching high electric potential, in the range observed in thunderstorms.

5. DISCUSSION

Summing up, electric fields enhance ice formation from water vapor, producing plenty of electrified particles that can further contribute to rapidly multiplying the electrified particles in the atmosphere. Then, there is positive feedback between electricity production and ice formation, as in an autocatalytic process. Fast charge accumulation within a given volume leads to Coulomb explosions and electrostatic discharge, thus explaining the explosive events observed in thunderstorms.

The enhancement of ice formation is the consequence of faster ice nucleation following the Classical Nucleation Theory (CNT) added to the occurrence of particle formation by a parallel non-Classical (NC) particle formation. The two mechanisms independently decrease or remove the supersaturated water vapor condensation barriers. That prevents the appearance of large pockets of metastability in the atmosphere. Also, both agents derive from the electrifying effect of ambient electric fields.

Excess charge in water lowers its surface tension [47] due to the repulsion between surface charges that oppose the attractive intermolecular forces. Following the CNT, reducing the surface tension also lowers the ice and water nucleation barrier, accelerating the water condensation. This is shown in (2),

$$R = N_s Z_j \exp(-\Delta G^*/kT) \quad (2)$$

where N_s is the number density of nuclei, Z_j is the probability that a nucleus at the top of the energy barrier will grow further, forming a stable particle, and ΔG^* is the energy barrier to the formation of nuclei, given by (3):

$$\Delta G^* = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \Delta g_v + 4 \pi r^2 \gamma \quad (3)$$

Moreover, the recent discovery of a field-dependent NC mechanism [46] for ice formation revealed that the electrification of small water molecular clusters creates an alternative path for ice formation limited only by diffusion and accretion, exempt from the limits posed by an energy barrier.

There remains to identify the origin of the electric fields that initiate the atmospheric electrification process. Some prospective contributors are:

a) The fields created by charge accumulated at aerosol particle-air interfaces within the Earth terrestrial field, following the Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars effect [29]. That shows that any interface within the atmosphere should get a positive or negative charge since it is within the Earth capacitor.

b) The fields are created by excess charge at the surface of water or ice during condensation or evaporation [48]. Knowledge of electrification during a phase change date from the 18th century, but it is not widespread. It derives from the weaker binding of $[\text{H}(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^+$ at water surfaces compared to $[\text{OH}(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$.

Fig. 6 represents the effect of environmental electric fields, multiplying atmospheric electricity through the acceleration of vapor condensation, and creating positive feedback loops that terminate as electric discharges or explosions during thunderstorms.

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of the feedback loop accounting for the production of high voltage in the atmosphere.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Electric fields enhance water vapor condensation within temperature and pressure gradients, producing electrified ice particles with high surface areas that contribute additional

electrification to the environment since their surface potentials reach the levels observed within thunderstorms.

Faster condensation of water vapor results from lowering water surface tension under an electric field that reduces or eliminates the energy barriers to vapor condensation, following the Classical Nucleation Theory and a recently discovered Non-Classical ice particle formation mechanism.

The initiators of the explosive processes of atmospheric electricity formation are thus water and ice particles that acquire charge and create electric fields that multiply the formation of new charged particles until an electric discharge or a Coulomb explosion occur.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] Galley, R.J.; Else, B.G.T.; Geilfus, N.-X.; Hare, A.A.; Babb, D.; Papakyriakou, T.; Barber, D.G.; Rysgaard, S. *Micrometeorological and thermal control of frost flower growth and decay on young sea ice, Arctic*, 68, 79-92, 2015.
- [2] National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC), "All About Sea Ice", <https://nsidc.org/cryosphere/seaice/characteristics/features.html>, April 2020.
- [3] Ponti, S.; Cannone, N.; Guglielmin, M. *Needle ice formation, induced frost heave, and frost creep: A case study through photogrammetry at Stelvio Pass (Italian Central Alps)*, CATENA, 164, 62-70, 2018.
- [4] Pidwirny, M. "Periglacial Processes and Landforms". *Fundamentals of Physical Geography*, 2nd Edition, 2006.
- [5] Korolev, A.; Isaac, G.A.; Hallett, J. *Ice particle habits in stratiform clouds*, Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc., 126, 2873-2902, 2000.
- [6] Williams, E.R.; Donovan, M.F.; Smalley, D.J.; Kurdzo, J.M.; Bennett, B.J. *Project Report ATC-447: "The 2017 Buffalo Area Icing and Radar Study (BAIRS II)"*, October 2019.
- [7] Finnegan, W.G.; Chai S.K.; Detwiler, A. *Enhanced and oriented riming of growing ice crystals*, The Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences, 61, 1976-1981, 2004.
- [8] Mason, B.J. *Snow crystals, natural and manmade*, Contemporary Physics, 33, 227-243, 1992.
- [9] Bailey M.; Hallett, J. *A comprehensive habit diagram for atmospheric ice crystals: Confirmation from the laboratory, AIRS II and other field studies*, Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences, 66, 2888-2899, 2009.
- [10] Field, P.; Lawson, P.; Brown, G.; Lloyd, C.; Westbrook, D.; Moisseev, A.; Miltenberger, A.; Nenes, A.; Blyth, A.; Choularton, T.; Connolly, P.; Bühl, J.; Crosier, J.; Cui, Z.; Dearden, C.; DeMott, P.; Flossmann, A.; Heymsfield, A.; Huang, Y.; Kalesse, H.; Kanji, Z.; Korolev, A.; Kirchgassner, A.; Lasher-Trapp, S.; Leisner, T.; McFarquhar, G.; Phillips, V.; Stith, J.; Sullivan, S. *Chapter 7: Secondary ice production – current state of the science and recommendations for the future*, Meteor. Monogr., 58, 7.1–7.20, 2017.
- [11] Lauber, A.; Kiselev, A.; Pander, T.; Handmann, P.; Leisner, T. *Secondary ice formation during freezing of levitated droplets*, J.Atmos. Sci., 75, 2815–2826, 2018.
- [12] Sotiropoulou, G.; Sullivan, S.; Savre, J.; Lloyd, G.; Lachlan-Cope, T.; Ekman, A.M.L.; Nenes, A. *The impact of secondary ice production on Arctic stratocumulus*, Atmos. Chem. Phys., 20, 1301–1316, 2020.
- [13] Miltenberger, A.K.; Lüttmer, T.; Siewert C. *Secondary ice formation in idealised deep convection — source of primary ice and impact on glaciation*, Atmosphere, 11, 542, 2020.
- [14] Korolev, A.; Heckman, I.; Wolde, M.; Ackerman, A.S.; Fridlind, A.M.; Ladino, L.A.; Lawson, R.P.; Milbrandt, J.; Williams, E. *A new look at the environmental conditions favorable to secondary ice production*, Atmos. Chem. Phys., 20, 1391-1429, 2020.
- [15] Finnegan, W.G.; Pitter, R.L. *Ion-induced charge separations in growing single ice crystals: Effects on growth and interaction processes* J. Colloid Interface Sci., 189, 322-327, 1997.
- [16] Bartlett, J.T., van den Heuvel, A.P.; Mason, B.J. *The growth of ice crystals in an electric field*. Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics (ZAMP), 14, 599–610, 1963.
- [17] Saunders, C. *Charge separation mechanisms in clouds*, Space Science Reviews, 137, 335-353, 2008.
- [18] Armstrong, W.G. *On the electricity of a jet of steam issuing from a boiler, letters to m. faraday*, Phil. Mag XVII, 370-374, 1840.
- [19] Buckley, J.R. "A Study of Heterogeneous Nucleation and Electrostatic Charge in Steam Flows", PhD Thesis, University of Birmingham (UK), 2003.
- [20] Schaefer V.J.; Cheng, R.J. *The production of ice crystal fragments by sublimation and electrification*. Journal de Recherches Atmosphériques, 5, 5-10, 1971.
- [21] Rydock, J.P.; Williams, E.R. *Charge separation associated with frost growth*, Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc. 117, 409-410, 1991.
- [22] Findeisen, W. *Über die entstehung der gewitterelektrizität*, Met. Zeit, 57, 201-215, 1940.
- [23] Findeisen, W.; Findeisen, E. *Untersuchungen über die eissplitterbildung an reifschichten*. Meteor. Z., 60, 5, 1943.
- [24] Libbrecht, K. G.; Tanusheva, V. M. *Electrically induced morphological instabilities in free dendrite growth*. Phys. Rev. Let., 81, 176-179, 1998.
- [25] Libbrecht, K. *A dual diffusion chamber for observing ice crystal growth on c-axis ice needles*, arXiv:1405.1384, 2014.
- [26] Libbrecht, K.G.; Crosby, T.; Swanson, M. *Electrically enhanced free dendrite growth in polar and non-polar systems*, J. Cryst. Growth, 240, 241, 2002.
- [27] Libbrecht, K.G.; Rickerby, M.E. *Measurements of surface attachment kinetics for faceted ice crystal growth*, J. Cryst. Growth, 377, 1-8, 2013.
- [28] Knight, C.A. *Ice growth from vapor at -5°C*, J. Atmospheric Sci., 69, 2031-2040, 2012.
- [29] Iwamoto, M. "Maxwell-Wagner Effect". In: Bhushan B. (ed.) *Encyclopedia of nanotechnology*, Springer, Berlin, p.1276, 2012.
- [30] Fermin, D.; Riley, J. "Charge in Colloidal Systems", Ch. 2 in Terence Cosgrove (ed.) *Colloid Science Principles, methods and applications*, Wiley, Chichester, 2010.
- [31] Galembeck, F.; Burgo, T. A. L. "Chemical Electrostatics", Chapter 4, Springer, Cham, 2017.
- [32] Peleg, Y.; Yoffe, A.; Ehre, D.; Lahav, M.; Lubomirsky. I. *The role of the electric field in electrofreezing*, The Journal of Physical Chemistry C, 123, 30443-30446, 2019.
- [33] Carpenter, K.; Bahadur, V. *Electronucleation for rapid and controlled formation of hydrates*, The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters, 7, 2465-2469, 2016.
- [34] Grabowska, J.; Kuffel, A.; Zielkiewicz, J. *The accretion of the new ice layer on the surface of hexagonal ice crystal and the influence of the local electric field on this process*, The Journal of Chemical Physics, 147, 174502, 2017.
- [35] Yang, F.; Shaw, R.A.; Gurganus, C.W.; Chong, S.K.; Yap, Y.K. *Ice nucleation at the contact line triggered by transient electrowetting fields*, Applied Physics Letters, 107, 264101, 2015.
- [36] Santos, L.P.; da Silva, D.S.; Galembeck, A.; Galembeck, F. *Ice needle nucleation and dendrite growth under an electric field*, IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications, 58, 2430-2435, 2022.
- [37] Carpenter, K.; Bahadur, V. *Electrofreezing of water droplets under electrowetting fields*, Langmuir, 31, 2243-2248, 2015.
- [38] Dalvi-Isfahan, M.; Hamdami, N.; Xanthakis, E.; Le-Bail, A. *Review on the control of ice nucleation by ultrasound waves, electric and magnetic fields*, Journal of Food Engineering, 195, 222-234, 2017.
- [39] Jha, P.K.; Sadot, M.; Vino, S.A.; Jury, V.; Curet-Ploquin, S.; Rouaud, O.; Havet, M.; Alain Le-Bail, A. *A review on effect of DC voltage on crystallization process in food systems*, Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies, 42, 204-219, 2017.

- [40] Budevski, E.; Staikov, G.; Lorenz, W.J. *Electrocrystallization, nucleation and growth phenomena*, *Electrochim. Acta*, 45, 2559–2574, 2000.
- [41] Bauerecker, S.; Buttersack, T. *Electric effect during the fast dendritic freezing of supercooled water droplets*, *J Phys Chem B*, 118, 13629–13635, 2014.
- [42] Reynolds, S.E.; Brook, M.; Gourley, M.F. *Thunderstorm charge separation*, *J Meteorology*, 14, 426–436, 1957.
- [43] Ribeiro, J.C. *On the thermo-dielectric effect*, *Anais Acad Bras Cienc*, 22, 325–347, 1950.
- [44] Amin, M.S.; Peterson, T.F.; Zahn, M. *Measurements of electric charge associated with evaporation and condensation of water on metallic surfaces as a consequence of pressure, humidity, and temperature change*, *J Electrostat*, 64, 597–603, 2006.
- [45] Paiva V.T.C.; Santos, L.P.; da Silva, D.S.; Thiago A. L. Burgo, T.A.L.; Galembeck, F. *Electric conduction and excess charge in silicate glass/air interfaces*, *Langmuir*, 35, 7703–7712, 2019.
- [46] Santos, L.P.; da Silva, D.S.; Galembeck, A.; Galembeck, F. *Electric fields enhance ice formation from water vapor by decreasing the nucleation energy barrier*, *Colloids And Interfaces*, 6, 13, 2022.
- [47] Santos, L.P.; Ducati, T.R.D.; Balestrin, L.B.S.; Galembeck, F. *Water with excess electric charge*, *Journal of physical chemistry C*, 115, 11226–11232, 2011.
- [48] Shavlov, A.V.; Dzhumandzhi, V.A.; Yakovenko, A.A. *Charge of water droplets during evaporation and condensation*, *J. Aerosol Science*, 123, 17–26, 2018.

8. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This INCT program of the Brazilian agencies MCTIC/CNPq (465452/2014-0), CAPES and FAPESP (2014/50906-9) supported this project. LPS thanks FAPESP (2019/04565-9) for a fellowship. The authors thank Prof. Earle Williams and Dr. James Rydock for their criticism and comments.